
Fakulteta za naravoslovje
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Research project

Analysis of Factors Influencing Young People's decisions for technical careers

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Košak, I., Šorgo, A., and Ploj Virtič, M. (2024). Differences in the career aspirations of Slovenian 15-year-old adolescents. *Education and Society in Transition: Addressing the Challenges of Youth and Technology*, 55-91.

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Introduction and problem definition:

Economic progress and the associated needs for certain professions have led to the emergence of new occupations and changing career paths. The shortage of educated personnel in technical professions is one of the fundamental challenges of societal development. Many countries are already facing a shortage of educated personnel in technical professions (Šorgo and Ploj Virtič, 2020). Occupations that are already in short supply in society or are predicted to be in short supply in the near future are called deficit occupations. The deficit of technical professions is not just a local problem; a large part of the world has been grappling with it for many years (Ivanova et al., 2019; Kozak, 2019; National Science Board, 2018; OECD, 2022; Ploj Virtič and Šorgo, 2022; Shvindt and Nikanorov, 2017; Šorgo and Ploj Virtič, 2020). Therefore, the primary concern of every society should be to attract and inspire young people to pursue technical careers. The decision to enter a technical career can be attributed to numerous factors, such as personal, interpersonal, environmental influences, etc. (Borrego et al., 2018; Cleaves, 2005; Davenport et al., 2020; Gero and Abraham, 2016; Jiang et al., 2019; Ploj Virtič and Šorgo, 2022; Šorgo and Ploj Virtič, 2020; Wei-Cheng et al., 1998; Woolnough, 1994; Woolnough et al., 1997), which need to be carefully examined to help find solutions to alleviate the shortage of these professions. Choosing the right educational path is the first step in a technical career, so one of the most important decisions that students must make at the end of primary education is choosing a high school. They have three possible choices. A student can: (1) terminate formal education, (2) continue education in gymnasium programs, or (3) continue education in programs of secondary vocational or professional schools. This choice can mark an individual's lifetime, as career paths initiated at that time almost invariably do not change significantly later on (DeGeorge and Fayolle, 2013).

The aim of our project was to:

1. Monitor and analyze the changing career aspirations of students from the fifth to the ninth grade of primary school in Slovenia,

2. Identify the factors influencing career aspirations and educational path choices of ninth-grade students in Slovenia,
3. Develop predictive models to recognize the influence of various factors on career aspirations and educational path choices of ninth graders in Slovenia.

Understanding and possibly influencing the decisions of students after completing elementary school to enroll in upper-secondary schools that enable the start of career paths in the technical-technological field (enrollment in a technical high school or after completing secondary school in a technical higher education program) is crucial for workforce planning.

Theoretical overview:

When choosing an educational path, young people make decisions based on various factors, such as their own interests, which define students' interests and activities, potentially indicating a decision for a specific education and profession (Ahmed & Mudrey, 2019; Jacobs et al., 1998), motivation, defined as the desire to achieve set goals (Ahmed & Mudrey, 2019; DeFeo, 2015; Tohidi & Jabbari, 2012), self-efficacy, which, according to Bandura, refers to an individual's belief in effectively performing a certain activity (the student knows their learning abilities and what they can achieve with them) (Bandura, 1986a; 1986b; Čot, 2004; Lent et al., 1994; Lent et al., 2017), experiences gained by the individual in their immediate environment which can influence the choice of educational and career paths (Rosenbaum, 1994), and so on. Career decisions and the significance of individual factors or their combinations are explained by several different theories. In the development and interpretation of the predictive model, we employed the following foundational theories: General Social Cognitive Theory of Self-Efficacy (Bandura, 1986a). Bandura's self-efficacy was incorporated into the 'Social Cognitive Career Model' by Lent and colleagues (1994), who developed the Social Cognitive Career Theory (Lent et al., 1994). The Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and its enhancement, the Reasoned Action Approach (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2011), are the next foundational theories we considered in the development of the predictive model.

In addition to the foundational theories, we also utilized some general theories and enhancements of foundational theories, such as: Bandura's (1999) concept of perceived self-efficacy and the classic definitions of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Based on these foundational and general theories, several models have been developed so far, exploring the influences of various factors to explain educational and career decisions

(Church et al., 1992; Gray & O'Brien, 2007; Janštova & Šorgo, 2019; Lent et al., 1994; Liñán, 2005; Liñán et al., 2011; Šorgo et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2008; Xing et al., 2019).

Methodology:

The project followed the following steps of research:

- Review of sources and theoretical frameworks.
- Development of a theoretical research model of career aspirations and decisions of elementary school students (PozelDON) and defining theoretical constructs or clusters.
- Formulation of research questions and hypotheses.
- Development of instruments to measure the influence of various factors on career aspirations and intentions of primary school students after acquiring a technical profession.
- Pilot and final surveys were conducted in the online environment 1KA.
- Piloting instruments on a smaller sample of ninth-grade students in Slovenian primary schools.
- Validation of instruments through statistical analyses.
- Analysis of career aspirations of students from 5th to 9th grade of elementary school in Slovenia. Descriptive, inferential, and multivariate methods of statistics were used (Field, 2013).
- Based on the initial theoretical model PozelDON, analysis of connections between individual factors and influences on career aspirations and intentions after acquiring a technical profession, and decisions of ninth graders regarding further education.
- Development and analysis of predictive models of career decisions of lower secondary school students.
- Based on the analysis of results, preparation of proposals for interventions and recommendations for further research.
- Analysis of limitations of the study.

Baseline research model of career aspirations and decisions of lower secondary school students »PozelDON«:

In the theoretical model PozelDON (Figure 1), we anticipated that factors such as gender, region of residence, size of the place of residence, and academic performance would influence (moderate) the relationships between constructs. Individual theoretical constructs (or their instruments) and their significance are described below.

The instrument "Personal factors for career choice" was designed with the aim of capturing as many possible factors, both internal and external, that could influence the choice of a career path leading to a desired profession. All statements of the instrument "Personal factors for career choice" are listed in the third section of the questionnaire for 9th-grade students in primary schools (Appendix 1).

The instrument "Attitude toward technical professions" provides a comprehensive insight into an individual's attitude toward technical professions, originating from internal and external factors reflected in the attitude. In developing the instrument, we drew upon theories (Ajzen, 1991; Lent et al., 1994) which we linked to attitudes toward professions. All statements of the instrument "Attitude toward technical professions" are listed in the fourth section of the questionnaire for 9th-grade students in primary schools (Appendix 1).

Figure 1: The theoretical model PozelDON

The instrument "Intention to choose a technical profession" expresses the effort that an individual will invest in choosing a technical profession and stems from motivational factors. All statements of the instrument "Intention to choose a technical profession" are listed in the fifth section of the questionnaire for 9th-grade students in elementary schools (Appendix 1). The instrument "Career aspirations" is a novelty in this field and provides information about the career aspirations of respondents: regarding fields of work and the level of education required by the profession. All statements of the instrument "Career aspirations" are listed in the eighth section of the questionnaire for 9th-grade students in elementary schools (Appendix 1).

The choice of further education is the outcome variable that provides information about the chosen secondary school. In the theoretical model, this variable represents expressed behavior.

Research sample:

In the non-experimental study, we included 4,534 students from the 5th to the 9th grade of 35 Slovenian elementary schools (aged 11 to 15 years), and data were collected using an online questionnaire. We systematically selected schools to include all regions (10 statistical regions: Pomurska, Podravska, Savinjska, Koroška, Zasavska, Posavska, Osrednjeslovenska, Jugovzhodna, Goriška, and Obalno-kraška), and we proportionally distributed the sample according to the size of the cities (villages, small towns, large cities). With a general questionnaire intended for all respondents, we monitored changes in the popularity of career aspirations in 13 professional fields alongside demographic data. Additionally, 9th-grade students answered questions about: (a) personal factors influencing career choice, (b) attitude toward technical professions, (c) intention to choose a technical profession, and (d) current choice of upper-secondary school. Both questionnaires are provided in Appendix 1.

Results:

The results are divided into three parts, where the first part contains the results obtained through descriptive statistical methods and the analysis of career aspirations of students from the 5th to the 9th grade of elementary school in Slovenia. The second part contains the results obtained through descriptive statistical methods of the sample of 9th-grade elementary school students and the analysis of (a) their career aspirations, (b) factors influencing career path choice, (c) attitude toward technical professions, and (d) intention to choose technical professions. The third part includes the development of predictive models of career decisions based on the data.

We found that in the entire population, the most popular professions are those requiring university or higher education, while professions requiring completion of elementary school are least popular. The most popular are professions in sports and culture, followed by technical-technological professions, and healthcare professions rank third in popularity. Over the years of schooling, the popularity of professions requiring university education increases, while the popularity of professions requiring completion of elementary school decreases. Career aspirations for technical-technological professions requiring high school education

noticeably increase from the 6th to the 9th grade. We also confirmed a stereotypical difference in career aspirations for technical professions between boys and girls.

Among 9th-grade elementary school students, technical-technological professions requiring university education rank third among the most popular professions, with statistically significant differences by gender favoring boys. Among the personal factors influencing the formation of career aspirations, it is worth noting that factors of internal (intrinsic) motivation prevail ("interesting work," "a profession I will enjoy," "a profession that will fulfill life ambitions," and "a profession that offers challenges"), while factors of external (extrinsic) motivation proved to be less important ("advice from others" and "profession brings fame"). In summary, we perceive that 9th-grade students generally have a very positive attitude toward technical professions, which is not reflected in their intention to choose technical professions, which is markedly low; statistically significant differences between genders are observed among boys.

By analyzing the obtained results, we verified the initial theoretical model PozelDON, which enables understanding the connections between individual factors and their influences on career aspirations and intentions after acquiring a technical profession, as well as decisions of ninth graders regarding further education. Figure 2 shows the verification of the initial theoretical model PozelDON.

Figure 2: Verification of the initial theoretical model PozelDON

Conclusions:

From the results of the study, we draw the following conclusions: students have shown a very positive attitude toward technical professions and have ranked technical-technological

professions among the most popular. However, these attitudes and aspirations are not reflected in students' intention to choose a technical profession or in their final choice of upper-secondary school, which would enable the beginning of an educational path toward technical professions.

A potential explanation for these results can be found in the research findings of authors Gibbons et al. (2004), which highlight that although students have a positive attitude toward STEM careers, they do not choose these professions because they lack sufficient information about technical professions. We would comment that they probably have good ideas about some (at least simpler and more widespread professions), while ideas about the work of engineers or developers are more vague. From the aforementioned research, it emerges that very few students were able to correctly list five different types of engineers, and none of them could provide entirely correct examples of the type of work performed by each type of engineer. These results are not surprising considering how rarely students reported hearing about engineering from their classroom teachers or other advising adults. Due to the lack of real information about technical professions, there is a high probability that students form misconceptions about these professions and consequently do not choose them. Additional research would be needed to explore the attitudes of parents, teachers, and school counselors toward technical and technological professions and to determine why they may not be discussing engineering careers with students. In Slovenia, we have not come across such research, and on a global scale, we found only one study in the USA (Gibbons et al., 2003), which found, in a survey of a sample of school counselors, that although they have a positive attitude toward technical and engineering professions, they have very little knowledge about technical and engineering careers.

It is becoming apparent that career aspirations cannot be explained by a single theory (e.g., Lent, 1994) and that too many factors are involved, ranging from personality factors within the domain of psychological sciences (e.g., Deci and Ryan, 2012) to numerous social and economic factors within the domain of social sciences (e.g., Lent, 1994), and also the objective reality of living and living environment. If the true goal of society and its subsystems is to bridge the gap between career aspirations and actual employment and the selection of technical careers, then delegating this problem to schools is not enough.

In conclusion, if the societal goal is to involve more students in the direction of technical-technological education and in continuing their career path in this direction, we must adopt

more effective interventions and measures, not only to promote interest in technical-technological professions among young people but primarily to convert their aspirations into concrete decisions. The responsibility for this must be taken on by the entire society with all stakeholders, who must spread objective and real information about technical-technological professions and careers they enable through various channels and media, and primarily provide decent opportunities for realizing career aspirations. Therefore, every stakeholder in society must play their role.

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